

The Relationship between the Transformational Leadership of Marketing Institutions and the Achievement of Competitive Advantage at the Health Sector (*Exploratory Study of Private Hospitals in Saudi Arabia*)

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the impact of relationship between transformational leadership and the achievement of competitive advantage through the three factors (consumers' satisfaction, consumers' loyalty, and the consumers' continuous use of health service at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and to achieve the objectives of the study researchers relied on the descriptive analytical approach and built a questionnaire as a tool to collect data from the study sample which was selected equally through the simple random sample method of the administrative employees from the three administrative ranks (upper, middle, lower) on the administrative levels at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Al-Hayat hospital in Jeddah, Al-Amin hospital in Taif, Abha private hospital, Makkah medical center hospital) based on the statistical samples schedule, where the researcher distributed (20) questionnaires on the administrative staff at the administrative ranks in the (4) hospitals that were selected equally with (20) questionnaires per hospital, therefore the number of distributed questionnaires were (80); in an appropriate and random method and all of those (80) questionnaires were recovered and consider valid for analysis. The results showed that impact level of relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of institution's institutional excellence at the health sector of the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia came with a high evaluation degree and an arithmetic mean for the sample members' responses of the employees in the three management levels (upper, middle, lower) between (4.23-4.39).The study also made some recommendations where the most important was the activation of the transformational leadership concept in the middle and lower administrative levels of marketing institutions in the health sector.

Keywords: *Competitive Advantage, Health Sector, Marketing Institutions, Transformational Leadership*

1. Introduction

The success of all health institutions, especially private health sector from health centers, hospitals, and clinics depends primarily on the administrative decision level, the capabilities of hospital's health leadership, and its ability to study the market (Abidi, Awni, 2009) in a way that achieve the interest and advantage of both patients and health institutions (Stevenson, William J. 2007). The success of this sector also depends on the qualified human resources who work inside this sector from the individuals in the specialty department in addition to the supporting medical services, speed, and techniques that individuals possess to achieve the main objectives of the private hospitals (Krajewski, Lee, J. & Rittman, Larry, P. 2005). Nowadays, Saudi Arabia has witnessed a significant growth and progress in both of the public and private health services but we should talk and focus on the private health sector due to the great efforts these private health institutions make to build and present the marketing, development, and corrective strategies in order to achieve the best benefits and the high quality for the private health services consumers (Atem, Tongwa Ivo & Yella, Gilbert, 2007) and also to achieve the maximum satisfaction degrees of their needs, and achieve the loyalty and belonging, and then continue to consume the banking service which lead the private health institution to obtain the competitive advantage.

When we talk about the leadership and its impact on the competitive advantage (Chase, Richard, B., Aquilano, Nicholas, J. & Jacobs, Robert, F. 2001) we will be talking about the corporate leaders who are mainly the decision-makers (Samir, Trigai, 2004) who have performed the miracles for institutions through the planned decisions they make which led significantly to the advancement of institutions in the health sector. The most important leadership theories that showed the importance of leader in the institutions (attributes or traits theory, contingency or situational theory, and interactive theory) where the theory of attributes tried to determine the leader internal and external characteristics but this theory couldn't provide a clear answers about these attributes (Atwi, 2001) while the contingency theory indicates that each leader suited to be successful at a certain time and circumstance and may not be successful during the future times

and circumstances (Al-Assaf, 2000), but the interactive theory indicates the ability of leader to interact with the components of definite situation (Al-Qaryouti, 2003), and due to the expansion of competition between the private health institutions, the owners of it have deliberately created an effective leadership which become a contemporary strategic leadership that achieved for these institutions a distinct level within the competitive environment.

The surrounding environmental challenges can topple many institutions which don't have wise leadership capable of making the required strategies for the current and future situation (Avolio, B. J. 1994) and given the importunacy of health service at the private hospitals due to its relationships with the human life in addition to the fact that health services are first-class human services and the organization must have a conscious and wise management leadership capable of building the most suitable strategies in the market to achieve the benefits and benefits for the consumer and the institution and thus achieve the competitive advantage.

(Stevenson, William, J. 2007) stated that continued interest in the transformational leadership concept through the participation in decisions by the leadership of the organization and the work on studying the business environment consider an advantage that only perform by the leaders at the hospitals higher management of the health sector, which comes after the identification of task and then the identification of long and short-term goals, where all of that depends on the ability of decision-maker to keep up with the environmental changes and developments to align with the consumers' desires of health services in order to achieve for them the human and medical aspect and then the satisfaction, happiness, loyalty, and the continuation of health service consumption through the same institution whenever needed.

Study Question: What is the relationship between leadership and the achievement of competitive advantage in the private health sector?
Transformational leadership methodology in the achievement of competitive advantage (Model)

Upon the above introduction, we can represent the impact of transformational leadership methodology as a creative analytical process connected to the shared mental activity between the management leadership and the leading managers of the departments and sections in a meaningful way to develop the organization and invest its capabilities in a healthy functional environment in order to achieve the organization and consumers objectives and then achieve the competitive advantage.

2. Procedural Terms

Transformational leadership: the followed mechanisms and the management possibilities and capabilities in making decisions in partnership with the administrative leaders to raise their morale and feelings towards the organization in order to build the strategies that align with the data of internal and external environment and in the interest of institution and the consumer which push toward the achievement of competitive advantage (Al-Khatib, Munther Hashem, 2007), while the definition of leadership is the conduct or behavior that leader practice for the goal of influencing the working individuals' behaviors to improve the quality of work (Al-Omyan, 2010).

Competitive advantage: is the enterprise's weapon in the market which invests in it to achieve a high level of satisfaction, loyalty, and the continuation of consumers to get the health services at the private hospitals which achieved through the benefits and advantages that health institution provides in services, prices, and promotional programs for the consumer group related to the organization.

3. Study Importance

Due to the intense competition that global markets generally witness in all sectors and particularly in the private health sector, the institutions have sought to significantly improve the quality of strategies where the only way to achieve this goal will be by focusing on the transformational leadership concept and activated it in these hospitals due to the things this concept achieves through the active participation between the senior leadership of the institution and other management leaderships which contribute to the decision-making process and lead to the achievement of competitive advantage. This research is concern with determining the relationship between transformational leadership at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia and achieving the competitive advantage of the institution from the standpoint of managers at the three management levels(upper, middle, and lower management).

4. Study Hypotheses

The researcher worked to derive the study hypotheses from the main study variables in the research title (the relationship between transformational leadership and the achievement of competitive advantage at the private health sector) where the factors related to the achievement of competitive advantage will be the following three secondary factors (consumers' satisfaction, consumers' loyalty, and the consumers' continuity of health services at the private hospitals) where the hypotheses will become as follows:

- There is a relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction with the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty about the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the profitability achievement at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.

5. Study Objectives

This study aims to achieve a set of secondary goals related to the main study topic where the goals were derive from the relationship between transformational leadership and the achievement of competitive advantage through the three factors (consumers' satisfaction, consumers' loyalty, and the consumers' continuous use of health service at the private hospitals) which ultimately contribute to the achievement of competitive advantage at the hospitals in the health sector, where the objectives were formulated as follows:

- Identify the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction with the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- Identify the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty about the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- Identify the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- Identify the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and profitability achievement at private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.

6. Study Model

Previous Studies

The study of (Zaghb, 2015) entitled "The role of administrative leadership at Nablus city hospitals in the implementation of total quality management" aimed to identify the administrative leadership role at Nablus

city hospitals in the implementation of total quality management, where the study results indicate an important and large role of the administrative leadership in the implementation of total quality management at Nablus city hospitals which drives toward the competitive advantage. The most important features of leadership: the participation in decision-making, the motivation of employees, and the enhancement of their realism where the study emphasized the need to focus on the administrative leadership in addition to the participation in decision-making, the establishment of specialized quality units at the hospitals in order to enhance the efforts, and implement the total quality management which leads to the competitive advantage in the market. One of the rewards and benefits of competitive advantage that it raises the enterprise levels at the market, which could be felt through the feeling of the organization about consumer satisfaction and then the loyalty of clients and consumers, which leads to the achievement of continuous customers communicate with the organization.

While the study of (Jeen & Hishamuddin, 2012) entitled "The competitive advantage and strong management performance in SMEs" aimed to identify the relationship between the competitive advantage and strong management performance in SMEs where the study results showed that prevailing theories in management have an impact on the achievement of competitive advantage and that relationship changes between the management and employees or between the management and customers have an impact on the performance and competitive advantage. Therefore, the competitive advantage has the strongest position among enterprises while many institutions have many obstacles in front of it due to the lack of investment in effective leadership which leads to the achievement of competitive advantage in a way that differentiates the institution from the other institutions at the market sector.

But (Chenwi, 2012) study about the impact of strategic leadership on organizational success methods at the public and private sectors, and the non-profit organizations aimed to compare the impact of strategic leadership at public and private organizations and non-profit organizations at all levels on the organizational success methods and the availability of effective organizational services. The study results showed a lack of interest in the management leadership and a lack of training practices, especially in the implementation of strategic leadership, which affects the level of competitive advantage where management leadership has the first and last role in the decision-making, which is the reason for the achievement of all the advantages in general and the competitive advantage in particular, taking into consideration that success of all the activities offered by the employees at the market depends primarily on the leadership decisions that achieve the competitive advantage of the institution.

The study of (Al-Ghazali, 2012) about the impact of transformational leadership at the Jordanian insurance companies aimed to detect this impact, by taking into consideration the following dimensions (ideal impact, motivation, individual authority, intellectual encouragement, and empowerment) on the effectiveness of decision-making process. To achieve the study goal researcher designed a questionnaire that consist of (39) items to collect the preliminary data from the study sample which contain the managers who work in the senior and middle management at the Jordanian insurance companies, where researcher distributed (489) questionnaires, (434) of those were retrieved, and (422) of it were valid for statistical analysis. The results showed that the availability level of the transformational leadership with its five dimensions at the Jordanian insurance companies has a positive impact on the effectiveness of the decision-making process. The study also highlighted that the ideal impact dimension had a major impact on the effectiveness of the decision-making process at the Jordanian insurance companies which has an impact on the achievement of the company's competitive advantage.

We can't deny that decision-makers have the greatest part in the institution's success which operate under their leadership and control, where the right decision made by leadership decision-maker in light of all changes and variables can create miracles and achieve the competitive advantage of institution.

While the study of (Ghafoor, et al, 2011) aimed to identify the relationship between transformational leadership and employees' participation and performance, and the relationship of psychological ownership dimensions (self-efficiency, belonging, self-identity, and accountability) with the performance of employees in order to achieve the competitive advantage in the market. The empirical study results of data that were collected from (270) questionnaires which were distributed on the study sample of employees and managers at the telecommunications companies in Pakistan indicates a positive relationship between the transformational leadership practice and employees' participation and performance, where the participation factor consider a motivation factor in making workers responsible for the duties and tasks they do, it

enhances their sense of organizational belonging, and the employees' participation practice in the transformational leadership framework leads to the development of positivity in the employees' behavior which results in the confidence, satisfaction, and the enhancement of belonging to achieves the competitive advantage. The psychological ownership and its dimensions, and the positive perceptions and beliefs that employees carry have implications on the organizational behavior of those employees which makes them feel part of the self-organization that increases their cooperation and increase the effectiveness of their performance which achieves the profitability and competitive advantage for the organization. One of the qualities of a leader is that he allows administrators to participate in the decision-making process, which leads to greater achievement in reaching tangible and intangible profits, and therefore creates the competitive advantage of the enterprise.

But the goal of (Algalbi & Mohammed, 2010) study was to reveal the impact of transformational leadership on the organizational innovation at the Jordanian cellular telecommunications companies (Zain, Orange, Umniah, Express), where the study adopted the descriptive analytical approach by using the practical applied method and the study sample consisted of all (120) departments' heads and specialists who work in these companies from the different majors. Some of the most important results of the study included that all transformational leadership behaviors were moderate at the Jordanian cellular telecommunications companies, the creativity adoption level and the availability of creative capabilities were at high level, and the existence of statistically significant impact of transformational leadership behaviors in their dimensions (ideal impact, intellectual encouragement, individual recognition, empowerment) on the organizational creativity with its variables (creativity adoption and the availability of creative capabilities), where the organizational creativity considers one of the difficult tasks that only the administrative leaders in the organization can accomplish, given that creativity participate effectively in the achievement of all organization gains and therefore achieve the competitive advantage.

The study that was performed by (Rose, 2007) aimed to identify the role of managers' management style in the study of work climate represented in the decision-making participation and work environment improvement, and study also aimed to identify the creativity related to the management and leadership style of manager and the level of organizational output. The study sample consisted of (218) managers at the Charles Stewart city in Australia and the study found a relationship between the management style of managers and both organization climate and work performance, and that democratic style in the work unit is positively related to the employees' performance at the work unit which has reflection on the competitive advantage levels of the organization and its success. The leadership style and leadership level vary from one enterprise to the other another which indicates the high level of competitive advantage ratio at one institution; on account of other institutions.

While the study of (Hatoug, 2006) entitled "A proposed model of the management role in the achievement of competitive advantage at the hotel and tourism education programs in the Jordanian community colleges in light of its reality and the contemporary trends" aimed to propose a model for the management role in the achievement of competitive advantage at the hotel and tourism education programs in the Jordanian community colleges. The study sample consisted of (83) administrators and faculty members who work at nine Jordanian community colleges that implement and execute the hotel and tourism education programs which spread over various regions of the Kingdom. After the suggestion of management role model to achieve the competitive advantage, the researcher concluded that management role at the Jordanian community colleges in achieving the competitive advantage in the hotel and tourism education programs reside in (13) areas, which are: the leadership, management methodology, competitive strategy, Organizational culture, organizational structure, human resources management, students' affairs management, technology management, infrastructure, knowledge management and research and development, partnership with stakeholders (clients), operations management in the fields of program implementation and execution, and quality control. The researcher recommended the need to focus on management leadership to achieve the competitive advantage which creates the loyalty and belonging of consumers, and then they will continue to deal with the services provided by the organization.

The study of (Al-Sakarneh, 2005) addressed "the leadership strategies and its role in achieving the competitive advantage and improving the performance of telecommunications companies in Jordan" given that business leadership is a characteristic of the management leaders. Study aimed to develop the leadership strategies that contribute to the achievement of competitive advantage and the improvement of

telecommunications companies' performance in Jordan, and to confirm that a model has been developed to test the relationships between the independent and dependent study variables where independent variables consisted of leadership strategies that contain (creativity, innovation, exclusiveness, risk taking, initiation) while the two dependent variables consisted of the competitive advantage which includes (differentiation, cost leadership, creativity, alliances), and performance which include (processes' improvement, employees' trends development, customers' service level improvement, growth and productivity). The field study data were collected through the study population which are represented in the (4) telecommunications companies that operate in Jordan, while the study sample consisted of (140) managers from the departments' leaders, where the study results concluded the existence of statistically significant relationship between the implementation of leadership strategies and the achievement of competitive advantage at the telecommunications companies.

Bowne (2004) study entitle "Organizational Structure and the Creative Process" suggests that innovative advantage developed by innovators can be a powerful source of competitive benefits in the businesses, arts, science, or life itself. In fact, the creativity, innovation, adaptability, and the change in organizational structures require first-class leadership managers and consider as the basis for success in several organizations. This study used a graphic model to verify the possible causes of the apparent separation between theory and observation where the model was implemented on simple and appropriate organizations in the United States, in order to verify the relationships between individual creativity, organizational creativity, and the organizational structure. There is a simple formula of the graphic model that has been analytically verified and there is also an upgraded formula that has been analyzed by using the Monte Carlo model where the results of the model showed that structure wouldn't necessarily give priority to the growing creative performance and showed that most profitable organizations are those which changed their structures to a highly integrated structure. The model showed that growth in individual creativity and creative leadership wouldn't be developed but in fact it's possible to decrease the organizational creativity, where the researcher recommended the need to focus on the leadership elements in the organization; such as innovation and development which in return raise the level of competitive advantage that will be achieved through the customer satisfaction.

7. Study Methodology

The study aimed to identify the level of relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage in the health sector through an exploratory study at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

8.1 Study Approach:

The researcher relied in this study on the descriptive analytical approach where the descriptive method describes a phenomenon to reach the causes of its occurrence and identify the factors that have an impact on this phenomenon while through the analytical method the researcher will collect data, analyze it, and use it to test the study hypotheses and then deduct the results and provide some recommendations, therefore researcher designed a questionnaire as a tool to collect data from the study sample.

8.2 Study Population:

The study society consists of a number of administrative employees who were selected equally from the three administrative ranks (upper, middle, lower) on the administrative levels at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

8.3 Study Sample:

The study sample was selected equally through the simple random sample method of the administrative employees from the three administrative ranks (upper, middle, lower) on the administrative levels at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia where the (Al-Hayat hospital in Jeddah, Al-Amin hospital in Taif, Abha private hospital, Makkah center medical hospital) were selected based on the statistical samples schedule at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and the researcher distributed (20) questionnaires on the administrative staff at the administrative ranks in the hospitals that were selected equally with (20) questionnaires per hospital, therefore the number of distributed questionnaires were (80); in an appropriate and random method and all of those (80) questionnaires were recovered and consider valid for analysis which is the number required to obtain the reliability, provide the results, and make the required recommendations.

8.4 Analysis Unit:

According to the nature of study variables, the analysis unit consisted of a random number of administrative employees at the selected hospitals where the study members response to the study tool that was designed by the researcher in order to collect data from the selected study sample; regardless of any demographic characteristics related to the study sample, such as different cultures, ages, or educational levels.

8.5 Data Collection Methods:

- **Secondary sources:** the researcher relied as secondary sources in the study theoretical framework on the books, documents, previous studies, Arabic and foreign references, electronic articles, and the masters' thesis and doctoral dissertations related to the study topic which represented in the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the competitive advantage at the private health sector.

- **Primary Sources:** The study was based on the questionnaire as a primary source to collect its data, which was specifically designed for the current study purposes by using the Five Likert Scale method and returning to the main study topic which examines the relationship between transformational leadership of the marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector, where the questionnaire was created based on studying the relationship between independent variable represented in the transformational leadership of the marketing institution and the dependent variable represented in the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector by examining the relationship between transformational leadership and its impact on the four dimensions: (consumer satisfaction achievement, consumer loyalty achievement, consumer continuous use of health service, and profitability achievement), where the study tool included (40) items to measure this relationship divided as follows:

Table (1) Items distribution of the relationship between the transformational leadership of the marketing institution and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector

Transformational leadership and its impact on	Consumers' satisfaction achievement	Consumers' loyalty achievement	Consumer continuous use of health service	Profitability achievement
Number of items	10	10	10	10
Order of items	1-10	11-20	21-30	31-40

Where the responses were between (1-5); according to the Five Likert Scale method as follows:

Table (2) responses' scale

Responses alternatives	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Degree	5	4	3	2	1

8.6 Study Variables:

The study consists of the following independent and dependent variables:

- **Independent Variable:**

The transformational leadership of marketing institutions through the administrative leadership levels (upper, middle & lower).

- **Dependent Variable:**

The achievement of competitive advantage in the health sector, and it consists of the following dimensions: (consumers' satisfaction achievement, consumers' loyalty achievement, consumers' continuous use of health service, and profitability achievement).

9. Statistical Analysis

To respond to the items and questions of the study tool and test its hypotheses, the researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and followed the descriptive-analytical approach, and implemented the following statistical methods and tests:

- **Frequencies & percentages:** in order to identify and analyze the adopted measurement indicators and scales in the study.

- **Arithmetic Means:** to determine the response level of study sample members on its variables and conduct the comparison process that the study aims to achieve.

- **Standard Deviation:** To measure the dispersion degree of study sample members' responses from its arithmetic means.

- **Category Length Formula:** To measure the importance level of study variables which were calculated through the equation:

Implementation degree (level of importance) = Higher degree – Lower degree/ Number of importance level

Implementation degree = $5 - 1 / 3 = 1.33$

Therefore, the level of importance will be as follows:

Table (3) the scale used to identify the appropriateness level of arithmetic mean

Arithmetic mean	Evaluation Degree
1.00-less than 2.34	Low
2.34-less than 3.68	Moderate
3.68-less than 5.00	High

- **Cronbach Alpha Coefficient:** to measure the constancy of study tool (questionnaire) and its internal consistency degree, and identify the credibility degree of responses on the questionnaire items.
- **Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) & Tolerance tests:** to confirm that independent variables are not highly correlated.
- **Multiple Regression Equation:** to identify the impact of an independent variable represented in the transformational leadership of the marketing institution on the dependent variable represented in the achievement of competitive advantage in the health sector.
- **Factor Analysis:** the factor analysis was used to verify the extent of belonging to the dimensions of questionnaire items and table (4) shows the perpendicular rotation matrix for the independent variable items represented in the transformational leadership of the marketing organization and its impact on the dependent variable dimensions represented in the achievement of competitive advantage at the organization in the health sector, which includes (4) dimensions that were measured using (40) items.

Table (4)

The perpendicular rotation matrix of the independent variable items and their impact on the dependent variable

Item Number	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
1	0.74			
2	0.68			
3	0.54			
4	0.44			
5	0.58			
6	0.54			
7	0.66			
8	0.47			
9	0.55			
10	0.68			
11		0.51		
12		0.43		
13		0.80		
14		0.56		
15		0.42		
16		0.78		
17		0.77		
18		0.85		
19		0.75		
20		0.71		
21			0.85	
22			0.77	
23			0.73	
24			0.62	
25			0.81	
26			0.86	
27			0.73	
28			0.62	
29			0.80	
30			0.55	
31				0.79
32				0.73
33				0.66
34				0.60
35				0.83
36				0.80
37				0.66
38				0.83
39				0.79
40				0.54

Matrix Determinant = 1.592, Keizer-Mayer-Oclean test (KMO) = 0.61, Bartlett's Test = 2028.051, significant level (Sig) = 0.000

It's clear from table (4) that all items ranged between (0.42-0.86) which all exceed the (0.4) value and according to (Hill, B. D., 2011) any correlation below (0.4) would be ignored as it considers weak correlations, where the perpendicular rotation led to the classification of questionnaire items into four factors: the first factor included (10) items where its branches were between (0.44-0.74), the second factor with (10) items that its branches were between (0.42-0.80) while the third factor included (10) items where its branches were between (0.55-0.86) but the fourth factor also included (10) items that its branches were between (0.54-0.83). It shows from table (4) above that the matrix determinant value equal to (1.592) which exceeds zero, while the value of KMO test equal to (0.61) which is greater than (0.50) and consider an acceptable value since it's greater than (0.60) but in regard to the Bartlett's Test value is reached (2028.051) at significance level (0.000) which is lower than (0.05).

- Study Tool Constancy:

The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was used to verify the internal consistency of the questionnaire items as it considers the most commonly used measurement by researchers to achieve this purpose.

According to table (5) the results indicate that the overall Cronbach Alpha Coefficient for the dimensions and items of relationship between the independent variable (transformational leadership of the marketing institution) and the dimensions of the dependent variable (the competitive advantage of health institution) amounted to (0.84) which is a good percentage as it exceeded (0.8) according to (Gliem & Gliem, 2003).

Table (5) Cronbach Alpha Coefficient for the questionnaire items

Field	Dimensions	Items	Cronbach Alpha
The impact of transformational leadership in	Consumers' satisfaction achievement	1-10	0.72
	Consumers' loyalty achievement	11-20	0.58
	Consumers' continuous use of health service	21-30	0.59
	Profitability achievement	31-40	0.53
Overall 0.84			

10. Study Results Display & Hypotheses Testing

This part presents the study results to identify the impact of relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector through an exploratory study of the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and by testing the study hypotheses, where the results came as follows:

10.1 Study Results:

Results related to the arithmetic means of study sample members' responses on the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institution and the institutional excellence at the health sector:

Table (6) arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample members' answers on the dimensions of the independent variable represented in the transformational leadership and its impact on the institutional excellence (n= 80)

The transformational leadership of the marketing institution		Mean	STDEV	Evaluation Degree
1	Consumers' satisfaction achievement	4.23	0.59	High
2	Consumers' loyalty achievement	4.34	0.65	High
3	Consumers' continuous use of health service	4.39	0.53	High
4	Profitability achievement	4.36	0.56	High
The transformational leadership of marketing institution and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector		4.33		High

It shows through table (6) the T-Test sample of the arithmetic means:

- The arithmetic means of the first study sample members' responses, which represent the administrative employees in the three administrative ranks (upper, middle, lower) equally on the administrative levels at the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia represented in the (Al-Hayat hospital in Jeddah, Al-Amin hospital in Taif, Abha private hospital, Makkah medical center hospital) about the dimensions of the relationship between the transformational leadership of the marketing institution and the institutional excellence at the health sector where the arithmetic means were between (4.23-4.39) at a high evaluation degree, where the order of dimensions according to the arithmetic means were as follow: Consumer continuous use of health service came with an arithmetic mean of (4.39) at a high evaluation degree, while profitability achievement came with an arithmetic mean of (4.36) at a high evaluation degree, and the consumer loyalty achievement came with an arithmetic mean of (4.34) at a high evaluation degree, but the

consumer satisfaction achievement came with an arithmetic mean of (4.23) and also at a high evaluation degree, where the arithmetic mean for the field dimensions as a whole amounted to (4.33) at a high evaluation degree.

- The standard deviation values indicated an agreement between the study sample members on the relationship impact between the transformational leadership of the marketing institution and the institutional excellence of institution at the health sector, where the researcher found that importance level for all dimensions was high and attributes that to the high services level of health sector at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia and that priorities of all management levels (upper, middle, lower) are very concerned with the consumer satisfaction about the health service quality provided at the hospital and are also very concerned about marketing the hospital in a way that shows the quality level of health services provided. In addition, it seeks to attract the largest number of consumers and make an attempt for continuous improvement in order to attract consumers and get their loyalty, and their continuous use of health service, therefore achieve the permanent satisfaction with the quality of services provided by the hospital.

10.2 Hypotheses Testing:

This section will deal with testing the study hypotheses, arrive at some results, and make recommendations.

Main Hypothesis: there is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) about the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage in the health sector. It will derive from this main hypothesis the following secondary hypotheses:

- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) about the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction with the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) about the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty about the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) about the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.
- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) about the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and profitability achievement at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia.

In order to verify the validity of main hypothesis and to show any existence of impact for the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector in Saudi private hospitals, the researcher conducted the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test in order to verify the nonexistence of statistical problems in the study data which could have negative reflection on the study hypotheses test, such as lack of adoption of the natural distribution of data and the existence of large correlation between the independent study variables, which could lead to the inability to interpret or predict the situation.

Table (7) normal distribution of study variables

	Variables	Kolmogorov Smirnov	Results
Transformational leadership	Consumers' satisfaction achievement	0.143	Follow the normal distribution
	Consumers' loyalty achievement	0.126	Follow the normal distribution
	Consumers' continuous use of health service	0.209	Follow the normal distribution
	Profitability achievement	0.190	Follow the normal distribution

It shows from table (7) the results of statistical analysis using the SPSS program, and by looking at the results the distribution of all variables is normal at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) where all the normal distribution ratios of all responses were greater than (0.05), which the adopted level in statistical study and study analysis. In order to diagnose and verify the nonexistence of high internal correlation between the independent variables, the researcher calculated the Tolerance Coefficient for each independent variable and

tested the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) where the VIF value should be less than (10) for all variables and the values of Tolerance must be greater than the indication level (0.05).

Table (8) Variance Inflation Factor and Tolerance tests for the dimensions of the independent variable

Transformational leadership	Tolerance	VIF
Consumers' satisfaction achievement	0.661	1.513
Consumers' loyalty achievement	0.684	1.464
Consumers' continuous use of health service	0.651	1.546
Profitability achievement	0.675	1.482

Table (8) shows that VIF values of all independent variables were less than (10), and the Tolerance value for all dimensions of the independent variable were greater than the value (0.05), which indicate the nonexistence of high correlation between the dimensions of the variable, where all of these dimensions can be used in the regression model, and can identify which one of these dimensions has a statistically significant impact on the dependent variable, and can calculate the percentage of this impact in case it exists. After confirming the nonexistence of a high correlation between the dimensions of the independent variable, the multiple regression formula can be implemented to test the main hypothesis and subhypotheses.

Table (9) Explanatory power/ summary model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	0.821 ^a	0.697	0.678	2.93430

a. Predictors: (Constant) consumer satisfaction achievement, consumer loyalty achievement, consumer continuous use of health service, and profitability achievement

Table (9) shows a statistically significant impact of the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of competitive advantage at the health sector where the correlation coefficient (R) value amounted to (0.821^a) which indicates the existence of correlation degree between the independent variable combined with the dependent variable, and the Adjusted R-Square value amounted to (0.6780) which represents the explanation value of independent variable ability on the dimensions of dependent variable as a whole, which means that impact of the transformational leadership of marketing institution explain amount of (70%) from the change that occurs in the achievement of institution's institutional excellence at the health sector of private hospitals in Saudi Arabia, therefore the acceptance of the main hypothesis.

Table (10) ANOVA test to verify the validity of the model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig
Between groups	1194.432	3	312.954	51.883	0.000 ^b
Experimental error	1772.656	77	23.22		
Overall variation	2967.089	78			

Table (10) indicates that the F-value test is equal to (51.883) at a statistical significance of (0.00), which is statistically significance value at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) therefore there is a variation in the ability of independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table (11) the coefficients impact of independent variables on the dependent variable

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	β	Std.Error	Beta		
(Constant)	78.292	7.203		10.734	0.000*
Consumers' satisfaction achievement	1.240	0.172	0.634	7.203	0.000*
Consumers' loyalty achievement	1.439	0.209	0.618	6.899	0.000*
Consumers' continuous use of health service	1.621	0.257	0.584	6.315	0.000*
Profitability achievement	1.805	0.265	0.613	6.817	0.000*

* Statistically significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Table (11) shows the following:

- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction at the

health services in the Saudi private hospitals, where the values of T , β are (7.203, 0.634) respectively, which are statistically significant values.

- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty at the health services in the Saudi private hospitals, where the values of T , β are (6.899, 0.618) respectively, which are statistically significant values.

- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at the health services in the Saudi private hospitals, where the values of T , β are (6.315, 0.584) respectively, which are statistically significant values.

- There is a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the relationship level between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the profitability achievement at the health services in the Saudi private hospitals, where the values of T , β are (6.817, 0.613) respectively, which are statistically significant values.

11. Study Results & Recommendations Discussion

This section discusses the results that researchers reached through the study, according to its questions and its hypotheses testing, and also provides a set of recommendations that were derived from the findings.

11.1 Results Discussion:

The responses on the study's first question: "What is the level and impact of the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of the institution's institutional excellence in the health sector?"

The results showed that impact level of relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of institution's institutional excellence at the health sector of the private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia came with a high evaluation degree and an arithmetic mean for the sample members' responses of the employees in the three management levels (upper, middle, lower) between (4.23-4.39). The researcher may attribute this result to the transformational leadership importance of the marketing institution and its impact on achieving the objectives of the institution, get more consumers, and achieve their satisfaction and loyalty due to the role of transformational leadership and its relationship with raising the level and quality of health services provided by the private hospitals within the competition and therefore the role it plays in the achievement of institutional excellence.

First study hypothesis: is there a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) on the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction with the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia?

The results showed a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' satisfaction about the health services at the Saudi private hospitals, where the researcher found that the concern about transformational leadership of marketing institution reflect positively on the achievement of consumers' satisfaction, which helps to bring more consumers of the health service and therefore take the institution up to the institutional excellence.

Second study hypothesis: is there a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) on the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty about the health services at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia?

The results showed a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' loyalty about the health services at the Saudi private hospitals, where the researcher found through the relationship between the transformational leadership of the marketing institution and the increase in consumers' loyalty to the health service that loyalty increases with the increased interest in the transformational leadership and improving it continuously.

Third study hypothesis: is there a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) on the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia?

The results showed a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the achievement of consumers' continuous use of health service at

the private hospitals, where the researcher may attribute this finding to the importance of transformational leadership that contributes to the consumers' continuous use of health service through providing variety of services and improving it which develops with the development of transformational leadership concept of marketing institution.

Fourth study hypothesis: is there a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) on the relationship between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the profitability achievement of health service at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia?

The results showed a statistically significant impact at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the profitability achievement of health service at the private hospitals in Saudi Arabia, where the researcher may attribute this finding to the importance of activating the transformational leadership concept that increases the institution's profits by providing outstanding services in the competitive market and offering new services to consumers.

11.2 Recommendations:

Based on the study results, the researcher recommends that decision-maker and senior management at the health institutions and private hospitals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia do the following:

- The activation of the transformational leadership concept at the middle and lower administrative levels of the marketing institution in the health sector.
- Conduct the training courses and workshops for the employees at the three management levels (upper, middle and lower) on the transformational leadership of marketing institutions and the methods to develop it.
- Conduct similar studies to find weak points and conduct studies on the consumers' satisfaction to identify the implementation quality level of transformational leadership in order to develop it continuously and achieve more institutional excellence.
- Receive the complaints and look into it seriously through the employees working at the three management levels and through the consumers who use the health services, and to study these complaints and respond to it due to its impact on the development of transformational leadership concept.

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